

25 d after maturity. Restorer lines IR9761-19-1R and IR29723-143-3-2-1R can be sown only 30 and 45 d after harvest, respectively. It is safe to market the hybrid seeds 30 d after harvest. ■

Significance of stigma exertion in enhancing outcrossing in male sterile rice lines

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An investigation undertaken to study the floral characteristics of male sterile lines will lead to better outcrossing and enhanced seed set. Eight cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines were used for the study. Floral characters such as rate of stigma exertion, stigma length and

width, stigmatic area, style length, and natural seed set of these lines were observed during the 1995 wet season.

The natural seed set in these CMS lines ranged between 1.86% in IR68275A and 10.6% in IR58025A, with a mean value of 5.59%. Among the floret characteristics studied, stigma exertion showed a predominant influence on seed set. The mean stigma exertion rate ranged between 6% in IR68275A and 48% in IR58025A. IR58025A, IR68281A, and IR67684A showed a significantly higher percentage of stigma exertion. The significantly higher seed set (10.6%) in IR58025A was attributed to its higher stigma exertion rather than to any other floral characteristics. The genotype with the least stigma exertion (IR68275A) recorded the lowest natural seed set (1.86%). Genotypes with a higher rate

of stigma exertion recorded a higher style length, as observed in IR58025A, IR68281A, and IR67684A. Even though stigma exertion and style length in IR67684A were higher than in other genotypes, seed set was low (4.1%), indicating the linkage factor involved with cytoplasm for male sterility. In IR64707A, multiple stigmas were recorded in 3% of the florets.

Our results indicated that, among floral traits, better stigma exertion should be given maximum importance when developing desirable CMS lines. IR58025A showed maximum seed set (47.68%) and maximum style length (1.22 mm). Although genotype IR67684A showed many favorable floral characteristics for high seed set, it is undesirable because of the interaction of genome and cytoplasm on seed set. ■

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management

Effect of N levels and time of application on grain yield of hybrid rice

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During the 1995-96 wet season and dry season, we studied the performance of three hybrids—KHR1, ProAgro 103, and MGR1—using Jaya and Rasi as standard checks. This study included

growth and grain yield performance at four levels of N (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg ha⁻¹). Three schedules of N application were followed: three splits (50:25:25% at basal, tillering and panicle initiation), four splits (25% N at basal, tillering, panicle initiation, and 50% flowering), and five splits (25% N at basal, tillering, and panicle initiation and the remainder applied in two equal splits at 50% flowering and 10 d later). Grain yield differences among the test hybrids and varieties were significant during both

seasons. The maximum grain yields were recorded for ProAgro 103, Vikas, KHR1, and MGR1. Rasi produced 5-14% less grain yield than ProAgro 103. Varieties responded linearly to applied N levels up to 120 kg ha⁻¹. Grain yield differences were not significant among different schedules of N application, indicating that more than three splits of N application are not required for higher grain production by hybrid rice in Vertisol soils. ■

Crop management

Three-drying cultivation of rice: a new technology for rice production in drought-prone areas

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Shandong, China, has a dry spring and rainy summer. In Linyi district, for

example, mean annual rainfall is 872-949 mm, of which 125-150 mm (15%) occur in spring and 560-600 mm (65%) in summer. Because of waterlogging in the wet summer period, grain yields of rainfed crops such as maize, soybean, or sweet potato were often poor in low-lying farming regions. When rice was dry-seeded late in spring after fall

wheat, the medium-duration rice varieties could not ripen because of the shortened growing period. It was difficult to grow rice seedlings because of the lack of water in spring. Therefore, only a fall wheat crop could be grown in the region.

This paper reports research examining the ability to raise rice seedlings,

The effect of drought treatments on growth and yield of rice variety A7929 at various stages of crop development in TDCR and conventional management.

Drought treatment stage ^a	Third-leaf stage		Seedling age (55 d)			Transplanting shock (d)	4 d after transplanting (roots)		Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000-grain wt	Unfilled grain (%)	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)	Compared with check (±%)
	Green wt of 100 plants (g)		Plant height (cm)	Tillers			No.	Mean length (cm)					
	Plant	Root		(%)	Three tillers (%)								
Early	26.5	8.2	21.7	87.2	21.2	0	7.3	4.0	81.3	31.9	4.3	684.7 ± 8.03**	+28.58
Middle	18.1	6.9	33.1	18.1	0	6	1.2	0.4	36.9	26.7	47.5	301.5 ± 10.28	-43.31
Late	17.9	6.2	32.4	17.6	0	5-7	1.1	0.36	56.9	26.4	23.6	413.5 ± 8.04	-22.36
Complete growth	27.1	8.4	22.1	85.9	18.7	0	6.8	3.8	22.7	26.0	43.6	270 ± 5.34	-49.3
Conventional	18.3	6.3	32.3	17.9	0	5-7	1	0.33	68.2	31.9	4.1	532.5 ± 7.76	100

^aEarly stage = emergence of seedling to jointing; middle stage = jointing to heading; late stage = heading to ripening. **S_d = 9.24, t = 16.47, P = 0.01, T = 9.925, 16.47 > 9.925 P < 0.01.

prepare the ricefield, and care for the crop in dry conditions and with less water. The resulting system is referred to as three-drying cultivation of rice (TDCR). The TDCR system was studied from 1965 to 1981. This system reduced the detrimental effects of drought stress and made it possible to rotate summer rice and fall wheat, both of which could produce a good crop. TDCR has now become a model for rice growing in semiarid regions of China. Results of this work and the procedures recommended follow.

Dry-raising sound rice seedlings

A test was designed to survey drought resistance of rice with spot observations in ricefields in 1973-77. This showed that rice could tolerate some drought at the seedling stage (see table). Mean plant height of dry-raised seedlings was only 21.7 cm after 50-55 d during the seventh leaf stage, but yields exceeded those of conventional management. Seedlings can be raised in the upland nursery during the 50-60 d before the wheat harvest. The seeding rate is 67.5-75.0 g m⁻² on clay soil and 45-60 g m⁻² on loam soil. The crop is irrigated 2-3 times in the seedling stage, each time with 37.5-45.0 L water m⁻².

Dry-raised seedlings use only 80-90% as much water as wet-raised seedlings.

Dry soil preparation of the ricefield

After the wheat harvest, the land is plowed, made level, and irrigated. Seedlings are then transplanted using the water used for land preparation.

Care of the ricefield

Summer rice needs only supplemental water during the rainy season. Ways to save water include (1) waiting to irri-

Area and yield of rice in Linyi district, Shandong, China, 1965-94. Conventional management was practiced from 1965 to 1981, the three-drying cultivation of rice (TDCR) was used partially from 1982 to 1987, and TDCR was used throughout the district from 1988 to 1994.

gate the field until 3 d after transplanting, and (2) watering the field only when no rain has occurred for 7 consecutive d during the rainy season. In this way, water consumption can be reduced by 40-50%. Fields usually need

to be irrigated 7-8 times with 450 m³ water ha⁻¹ each time in the growing period. When drought is severe, up to 10 irrigations may be required to obtain high yields.

Impact on rice production

Since the late 1970s, drought has caused drastic cuts in rice area in Linyi (see figure). After 1982, TDCR became more popular and by 1988 was used by all farmers. Ricefields multiplied and rough rice yield increased year after year. By 1994 there was a 33% and 26% increase in per unit area yield compared with before 1982 and up to 1988, respectively. Yields of wheat following rice also increased from 1.5 to 5.4 t ha⁻¹. Therefore, profit increased by 22%.

Yield increased because the dry-raised seedling itself was healthy and mid-late rice cultivars would be planted in time to use their 20-d-longer growth period. Pests and diseases are insignificant and rotation cropping is improved.

TDCR has several advantages: (1) it is economical in water, labor, seeds, and energy; (2) it reduces costs and labor; and (3) it ensures a good harvest despite drought or waterlogging. ■

Agronomic package for hybrid rice cultivation

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Yield stagnation or even a decline has been observed in many rice-growing areas, particularly in potentially highly productive areas. To increase rice production, a few rice hybrids have been developed and released in recent years in India. To exploit the crop's full heterotic potential, it is essential to develop a package of optimum production practices for hybrid rice cultivation. We therefore attempted to study nursery management, seeding densities, seedling ratios, transplanting dates, N management, and hybrid response at several locations under the coordinated rice improvement program.

The studies revealed that the optimum seed density of 15-20 kg in a 1,000-m² nursery and planting in the second fortnight of July (1 seedling

hill⁻¹) are ideal practices for obtaining superior grain yield in hybrids. The results also indicated that different rice hybrids performed well at different locations: Hybrid ProAgro at DRR and Faizabad; ProAgro and CRH1 at the Central Rice Research Institute and Chinsurah. The local standard HKR46 performed well at Kaul. These hybrids recorded superior grain yields and showed higher N use efficiency at these locations. Grain yield differences in the tested hybrids were not significant at Aduthurai, Mandya, and Pantnagar. As

the tests were made in the wet season, the hybrids may not have exhibited their full yield potential at Cuttack and Maruteru because of rain. The response to N was limited up to 100 kg N ha⁻¹ at Cuttack, Chinsurah, and Pantnagar, and up to 150 kg N ha⁻¹ at Aduthurai, Hyderabad, Mandya, and Faizabad. Hybrids failed to respond beyond 150 kg N ha⁻¹ at most test locations. Applying the recommended N in three splits (50% basal + 25% tillering + 25% booting) was the best management practice for hybrids in Vertisols at DRR. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — weeds

Chemical weed control in rice nurseries of the hill zone of Karnataka

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Weeds pose a threat to rice cultivation from the nursery stage in the hill zone of Karnataka (south India), which has 182,000 ha under rainfed rice (the sole food and field crop of the zone). This area is located between 12-14° N and

74-76° E. Average annual rainfall is 2,460 mm, of which 83% occurs between June and September (with the remaining 17% from October to December). Rice nurseries are sown from the first week of June to the second week of July depending upon the toposequence and rainfall pattern for the wet season and during the second week of December to the second week of January for the summer (dry) season.

Rice nurseries are infested by grass sedges and broadleaf weeds that

Table 1. Effect of herbicides on germination of rice and dry weight of rice seedlings in the hill zone of Karnataka, India.

Treatment	Germination (%) recorded at 10 DAS ^a				Mean of 2 yr	Dry weight (av) of 10 seedlings at 25 DAS (g)				Mean of 2 yr
	Kharif (1993-94)		Summer (1994-95)			Kharif (1993-94)		Summer (1994-95)		
1. Control, unweeded check	92	94	94	95	94	1.06	1.13	1.12	1.27	1.19
2. Butachlor preemergence 50 EC (1.25 L ha ⁻¹)	92	94	88	92	91	2.39	2.43	2.43	2.67	2.55
3. Benthocarb-30 EC (1.25 kg ai ha ⁻¹) preemergence	74	76	68	72	72	1.84	1.94	1.96	2.01	1.98
4. Pendimethaline 30 EC (preemergence) (1.0 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	72	73	68	64	69	1.92	1.82	2.01	1.98	1.99
5. Butachlor (5%) granules (25 kg ha ⁻¹)	73	74	77	79	75	2.12	1.93	2.20	2.08	2.14
6. Anilophos 30 EC @300 mL ha ⁻¹ (3 DAS) Postemergence	89	93	90	88	90	2.26	2.33	2.32	2.46	2.39
7. Hand weeding at 10 and 20 DAS LSD (P = 0.05)	92	93	93	94	93	1.94	2.03	2.10	2.19	2.14
						0.03	0.08	0.12	0.27	0.16

^aDAS = days after sowing.